

BAZI TİCARİ RETANSİYON KİMYASALLARININ KARAKTERİZASYONU VE FLUTİNG KAĞIT ÖZELLİKLERİ ÜZERİNE ETKİLE

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ÖZET

Bu çalışmada, bazı ticari retansiyon kimyasallarını karakterize etmek ve bu kimyasalların fluting kağıtların fiziksel özellikleri üzerine etkilerini araştırmak amaçlanmıştır. Retansiyon kimyasalları üretim prosesi verimliliğinde ve ürünlerin kalitesinde önemli bir etkiye sahip olabilmektedir. Bu çalışmada, 3 farklı ticari firmaya ait retansiyon kimyasalları (10CE, 40CE ve Eka NP-PL-ATC) kullanılarak 100, 110, 120 ve 135 gr/m² gramajlarında fluting kağıdı üretimi yapılmıştır. Bu kağıtların fiziksel özellikleri belirlenerek retansiyon kimyasallarının bu özellikleri üzerine etkileri incelenmiş, retansiyon ve drenaj performansları da ayrıca belirlenmiştir.

Elde edilen sonuçlara göre, Eka Np-PL-ATC retansiyon kimyasalı diğerlerine göre daha iyi sonuçlar vermiştir. Eka NP-PL-ATC retansiyonu kullanılarak üretilen 135 gramajındaki fluting kağıtların dikey ezilme (CCT), yatay Ezilme (CMT) ve patlama mukavemeti değerleri sırasıyla 2.10 (kN/m), 280 (N) ve 2.88 (kg/cm²) olarak bulunmuştur. 10CE, 40CE ve Eka NP-PL-ATC kimyasallarının retansiyon değerleri ise sırasıyla %74, %83 ve %85 bulunmuştur. Drenaj performansı bakımından en iyi sonuçları 85 (ml/s) ile yine Eka NP-PL-ATC retansiyon kimyasalı vermiştir. Bununla birlikte, retansiyon miktarındaki artışa paralel olarak elek altı suları temizlenmiş, deşarj suyundaki kirlilik azalmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Retansiyon kimyasalları, fluting kağıt, fiziksel özellikler, drenaj

CHARACTERIZATION OF SOME COMMERCIAL RETENTION AIDS AND THEIR EFFECTS ON THE FLUTING PAPER PROPERTIES

ABSTRACT

The objective of this study was to characterize some commercial retention aids and to investigate effects on fluting paper properties. Retention aids can have a profound effect on the efficiency of the process and on the quality of the product. In this study, three different commercial retention aids (10CE, 40CE, and Eka NP-PL-ATC) were used in fluting paper production and the fluting papers with grammages of 100, 110, 120, and 135 gr/m² were produced by using these retention aids. Then, the physical properties of fluting papers were determined and effects of the retention aids on the physical properties of the papers were examined. Besides, effects of retention aids on the retention and drainage performance during paper production process were investigated.

The results showed that the physical properties of fluting papers by using Eka NP-PL-ATC retention aid were found to be better than those of the others. Corrugated Crush Test (CCT), Corrugated Medium Test (CMT), and bursting strength values of the fluting papers with grammages of 135 gr/m² by using Eka NP-PL-ATC were found as 2.10 (kN/m), 280 (N), and 2.88 (kg/cm²), respectively. The retention values of 10CE, 40CE, and Eka NP-PL-ATC were 74%, %83, and 85%, respectively. Eka NP-PL-ATC retention aid was more effective compared with each other. Eka NP-PL-ATC gave the best result in the drainage performance as 85 (ml/s). It was also observed that white water was cleaned and contaminants of the discharged water were decreased by adding retention chemicals.

Keywords: Retention aids, fluting paper, physical properties, drainage,

Introduction

Corrugated cardboard is the most popular packaging in the world for the storage and distribution of goods. It is two outside papers with a corrugated shaped paper in between. The outer papers are known as liners and the corrugated shaped paper is known as fluting or medium paper. Corrugated board can also be produced with two or three layers to increase its strength (Mark, 2013). Fluting paper is the middle liner of corrugated board, which can be supplied individually as a type of protective packaging. It provides protection by filling the empty spaces in the outer box and ensuring a cushioning effect for the primary product. It is an eco-friendly alternative to traditional packaging materials such as bubble wrap and other plastic-based materials. Its basis weight is generally between 90 and 140 gr/m² (Sefidgaran et al., 2006; Sarkhosh and Talaeipour, 2011).

Corrugated cardboard is widely used in the packaging industry. Its main advantages are lightness, recyclability and low cost. This ensures that the material is the best choice for producing containers dedicated to the shipment of goods. Approximately 2 million tons of corrugated cardboard is produced in Turkey. For this reason, fluting paper used in corrugated cardboard production has an important role in the paper industry. Since corrugated cardboard is mostly used in product transportation, it is exposed to external influences during transportation and therefore the paper must have high resistances. Because there is little or no pulp production in Turkey, almost all corrugated board is made of waste paper in Turkey. The fibers become shorter during recycling and the papers produced from these fibers have less strength than virgin fibers. Paper-makers use a variety of chemicals to overcome the resistance properties of recycled paper. The most important of the chemicals used for this purpose is retention chemicals (aids).

As the paper and board industry continues to increase the speed and output of paper machines, the demands on retention and drainage aids are increasing greatly. Increased shear forces at the headbox and on the wire and ever shorter dewatering zones can be incompatible with the need for good runnability, high quality and good formation. The drainage (dewatering) of pulp suspension is an important parameter that has a direct influence on the speed of the paper machine and the energy consumption of the drying process and paper-makers want the water in the suspension to move away quickly (You et al., 2016). Retention increases first-pass retention of fillers and fines and ash content of the sheet and reduces losses to effluent. Drainage effects wire section, press section and dryer section water removal (Thorn and On Au, 2009). Retention is closely related to quality characteristics such as paper gluing, opacity, porosity, color, strength (folding, breaking, etc.) surface smoothness. Lots of retention aids have been produced to improve retention and reduce costs. Retention aids are used to retain filler and fines in the wet paper web during the forming process, by aggregating these stock components to larger units. Hence, retention aids also cause fibers to aggregate, which deteriorate mass formation (Lancaster, 1998). The objective of this study was to characterize some commercial retention aids (10CE, 40CE, and Eka NP-PL-ATC) and determine effects on the properties of fluting paper by using these retention aids.

Material and Method

Material

Fluting papers with grammages of 100, 110, 120, and 135 gr/m² were taken from Kahramanmaraş Paper Mill. Three retention aids (10CE, 40CE, and Eka NP-PL-ATC) are supplied from a commercial firm is located in Turkey. The retention values were determined during fluting paper production in the paper mill. The physical and drainage performance tests were performed in the laboratory environment.

Methods

The fluting papers were produced by recycling waste paper containing 70% old corrugated cardboards and 30% mixed waste paper. These waste papers were pulped at 4-5% consistency, beaten to specified freeness levels and transferred to paper machine with adding some chemicals and the retention aids. Retention aids dosages were set as 400 gr/ton and fluting papers with different grammages were manufactured in fourdrinier paper machine at specific parameters. Papers and boards, being hydrogen-bonded assemblages of cellulose fibers, can be significantly affected by water vapor in the air surrounding the test specimen (Borch et al., 2001). The papers were conditioned at 23 ± 1 °C and 65% relative humidity in conditioning room accordance with TAPPI T 402 om-88 standard before the physical tests.

Some important physical properties such as corrugated crush test (CCT), corrugated medium test (CMT), and burst strength (Levin and Söderhjelm, 1999; Marin et al., 2009) were performed on the fluting papers accordance with TS 12735, TS 6717 EN ISO 7263, and TS 3123 EN ISO 2759 standards, respectively (Anon., 2001; 2002; 2004).

The drainage performance was evaluated by Schopper-Riegler degree (°SR), an important parameter for the drainage. Low °SR is better for dewatering of the pulp suspension (Chi et al., 2007). The °SR values were determined by using YT-DJ-100 beating tester, according to ISO 5267-1 (ISO, 1999). The drainage performances were measured by the amount of the water (ml) passing through sieve of SR tester in five seconds.

There are two types of retention, the First Pass Retention and General Retention. The First Past Retention values were used in this study and it can be calculated with the headbox consistency and the white water consistency. There is a very wide diversity of first-pass retention on different paper machines, from less 50% to almost 100%. First Pass Retention values were calculated by the following equation (Kosonen, 2004);

$$FPR = \left(\frac{HB-WW}{HB} \right) * 100 \quad (1)$$

FPR: First Past Retention Value, HB: Headbox Consistency, WW: White Water Consistency

Effects of retention aids on the retention values, drainage performances, and physical properties of the fluting paper were determined and compared with each other.

Results and Discussion

The retention values obtained from the addition of retention aids during the production of fluting papers with different grammages were given in Table 1. When the values in the table were examined, the effects of retention aids on the first past retention values can be easily understood. The best values are generally obtained during the production of high-weight (135 gr/m^2) fluting papers. Reduction in grammages also decreases the retention of filler and increases the frequency of sheet breaks both on the paper machine and during converting and printing. In comparison of retention aids, the properties of 135 gr/m^2 fluting papers were examined to minimize the error margin.

Table 3. The retention values during the fluting paper with different grammages production

Grammages	Retention Values (%)			
	Control	Eka NP-PL-ATC	40CE	10CE
100	72	80	77	70
110	64	85	73	65
120	76	83	81	80
135	76	85	83	74

Retention value was found to be 76% in the control trial in which the retention aid was not added. Eka NP-PL-ATC retention aids gave the best result in first past retention value as 85%. These values were found as 83% and 74% by using 40CE and 10CE, respectively. Retention aids added during the paper production increased the first past retention values by approximately 11%. According to Table 1, the best results were obtained with the addition of Eka NP-PL-ATC when compared with other retention aids. It was reported that retention aids increased the retention values in studies conducted on this field (Pelton et al., 1980; Tanaka et al., 1993; Forsberg and Strom, 1994; Ven, 1997; Qasaimeh et al., 2014).

The drainage performances of Eka NP-PL-ATC, 10CE, and 40CE were found as 80, 70, and 65 ml/5s, respectively. As in the case of retention value, Eka NP-PL-ATC has been more effective than other retention aids in drainage performance. The physical properties of the papers show improvements along with shortening of the drainage period (You et al., 2016). The drainage (dewatering) refer to the removal of water from the wet web during the formation of paper and has a direct impact on machine speed. The machine speed affects the amount of production. Therefore, the low drainage time is desirable for paper-makers and the best drainage performance was obtained by using Eka NP-PL-ATC in this study.

Table 4. The physical properties of the paper produced by using different retention aids

Grammages and Retention aids	CMT (Newton)		CCT (kN/m)		Burst Strength (kg/cm ²)	
	Mean Value	Standard Deviation	Mean Value	Standard Deviation	Mean Value	Standard Deviation
100 g/m ² 10 CE	167.27a	5.71	1.18a	0.03	2.01a	0.08
100 g/m ² 40 CE	158.11b	2.85	1.14b	0.03	1.89b	0.08
100 g/m ² Eka NP-PL-ATC	172.00c	3.08	1.26c	0.02	2.20c	0.08
110 g/m ² 10 CE	204.25a	4.62	1.31a	0.02	2.33a	0.10
110 g/m ² 40 CE	197.00b	3.79	1.37b	0.02	1.99b	0.08
110 g/m ² Eka NP-PL-ATC	216.30c	4.40	1.53c	0.03	2.41c	0.08
120 g/m ² 10 CE	242.00a	8.07	1.75a	0.03	2.48a	0.09
120 g/m ² 40 CE	227.00b	4.65	1.52b	0.02	2.29b	0.09
120 g/m ² Eka NP-PL-ATC	280.38c	3.29	1.81c	0.02	2.67c	0.10
135 g/m ² 10 CE	257.00a	3.27	1.88a	0.03	2.69a	0.08
135 g/m ² 40 CE	237.88b	4.16	1.78b	0.02	2.49b	0.09
135 g/m ² Eka NP-PL-ATC	280.00c	4.15	2.10c	0.03	2.88c	0.11

*Mean values with the same lower-case letters are not significantly different according to Duncan's mean separation test

The physical properties of the fluting papers produced by using the retention aids were presented in Table 2. As mentioned above, the physical properties of the fluting papers were improved with shortening of the drainage periods and increasing retention values. Roy et al., (2006), Tutus et al., (2016), and Ordonez et al., (2009) reported that the physical properties of the papers were increased by using retention aids. When the table was examined, the physical properties of the papers produced using Eka NP-PL-ATC were found to be higher than others. In order to determine statistical effects of retention aids on the physical properties, the Variance Analysis and Duncan Tests were applied. According to Duncan's mean separation test, there are significant differences with each other on 5% level of Duncan's test.

Conclusion

Waste papers are mostly used in corrugated cardboards production and have lower strengths than virgin pulp. Paper-makers generally use some chemicals to enhance paper strength and want to improve retention and drainage performance. Retention and drainage performance have effects on effluent, first pass retention of fillers and fines, ash content of the papers, wire section, press section and dryer section. Depending on all these parameters, they also affect the physical properties of the paper. The results of this study indicated that using the retention aids during fluting paper production has important roles in terms of paper strength properties, retention and drainage performance. Besides, white water was cleaned and contaminants of the discharged water were decreased by adding retention chemicals. As a result, it was determined that Eka NP-PL-ATC has an effect on the retention, drainage performance and physical properties and it is more suitable for fluting paper production than other aids.

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